

Comparative Analysis of Social Protection Intervention and Early Child Marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State.

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Abstract

The paper titled comparative analysis of social protection intervention and early child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State explored the nexus between social protection and multiple drivers of child marriage. 3 research questions were formulated which were translated to 3 hypotheses thus: Increasing school enrollment to offset time spent in participating in domestic labour has no significant relationship with child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area; sustainable household income support through cash /asset transfer has no significant relationship with child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area and civil Society Organization's child protection service has no significant with early marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area. The descriptive survey design approach was adopted. The sample for this study consisted of 400 respondents selected through the use of Taro Yamene's (1967) formula. The multi stage sampling procedure was used to select the sample of the study. A 4 likert scale questionnaire was the instrument for data collection and Chi square was for analysis. Findings revealed that social protection intervention have significant moderating and modulating influences on early child marriage. It was concluded that early marriage serves as a threat to a child's future development because it is difficult to have access to quality education and higher education and it limits the ability to secure a good job. Thus, it recommended amongst others that policy makers should improve social welfare for girls especially promoting school enrollment for them to pursue education

Keyword: Social protection Intervention, Early child marriage, Increased school enrollment

Introduction

Child marriage happens in all parts of the world and is not associated with any particular culture or religion. It is rooted in harmful gender norms and discrimination against girls and women. It is not a single phenomenon and covers a wide range of relationship types, each with its own causes and drivers, risks and preventive factors that often vary depending on setting and circumstance. Depending on the specific manifestations of child marriage, it may be seen as a manifestation of violence against children, sexual and gender-based violence, child trafficking or sexual slavery and other exploitative practices. Although voluntary unions between consenting adolescents are common in some areas. When marriages are forced, take place without the consent of the child, and are the result of physical or emotional pressure, they are regarded as a form of violence against children that disproportionately exposes girls to physical, sexual and emotional violence that must be prevented or responded to. (UNICEF, 2017)

In some jurisdictions, marriages of this kind are recognized as a form of violence that requires safeguarding and the intervention of child protection authorities. Voluntary early unions are commonly attributed to a lack of opportunities for young people or a negative coping strategy in response to economic hardships. In light of these explanations, in many cases, they may reflect a lack of options rather than a true choice. Child marriage is a violation of human rights. It has severe negative consequences for girls and women– including for their health, development, power, participation and safety – and for wider society including reduced economic growth.^{1,2} Child marriage prevalence has declined globally over the past 30 years, but progress has been uneven and too slow to meet the Sustainable Development Goal of ending the practice by 2030.^{3,4} In

addition, 10 million more girls are predicted to marry by 2030 due to the social and economic impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic (UNFPA-UNICEF, 2020)

Child protection is grounded in children’s rights and works for the protection of all girls and boys from birth to adulthood. The best interests of the child are a primary concern and require that child protection approaches are age-appropriate, recognize children’s evolving capacities and are tailored to the specific child marriage risks experienced by girls and boys of different ages. Protection risks increase in forced marriages, for girls married to older men, younger adolescent girls, pregnant adolescent girls, adolescent mothers, and for adolescents who are divorced or separated. Boys are also subject to forced marriage – although in lower numbers –and their needs and interests should also be addressed in child protection interventions. Child protection supports children’s rights to information, expression and involvement in the decisions that affect them, so they can better protect themselves (CEDAN & UNCRC, 2014).

Child protection goes beyond stand-alone sector-specific and issue-based approaches to child wellbeing. Child protection systems, services and approaches at community and district levels are designed to prevent and respond to all forms of abuse, violence and exploitation of children, including child marriage. Child protective response services go beyond prevention to ensure that the most vulnerable children are protected. This includes the provision of comprehensive services for girls who are married, pregnant and mothers, including safety and protection, health and psychosocial care, education, economic support, and justice (UNICEF, 2011).

While some boys marry before the age of 18, the vast majority of children who marry are girls, often against their will and with grave consequences. It is recognized that ending child marriage involves tackling the many challenges that perpetuate this rights violation, such as gender inequality and discrimination, lack of education, and poverty. Also, support for development and participation of adolescent girls, strengthening legal systems to protect the rights of adolescent boys and girls; carrying out cutting-edge research to build a robust evidence base for advocacy, policies, programmes and tracking progress ;strengthening services to help adolescents at risk of, or affected by, child marriage, particularly girls, and raising awareness of the need to invest in and support girls, and shifting the social expectations that stifle their prospects.

Child marriage happens in all parts of the world and is not associated with any particular culture or religion. It is rooted in harmful gender norms and discrimination against girls and women. It is not a single phenomenon and covers a wide range of relationship types, each with its own causes and drivers, risks and preventive factors that often vary depending on setting and circumstance. Evidence shows that effective app roaches must be tailored to the specific contexts in which girls, boys and families live (Stoner, 2019) Depending on the specific manifestations of child marriage, it may be seen as a manifestation of violence against children, sexual and gender-based violence, child trafficking or sexual slavery and other exploitative practices. Although voluntary unions between consenting adolescents are common in some areas, when marriages are forced to take place without the consent of the child and are the result of physical or emotional pressure, they are regarded as a form of violence against children that disproportionately exposes girls to physical, sexual and emotional violence that must be prevented or responded to. In some jurisdictions, marriages of this kind are recognized as a form of violence that requires safeguarding and the intervention of child protection authorities (Handa, 2014).

The best interests of the child are a primary concern and require that child protection approaches are age-appropriate, recognize children’s evolving capacities and are tailored to the specific child marriage risks experienced by girls and boys of different ages. Protection risks increase in forced marriages, for girls married to older men, younger adolescent girls, pregnant adolescent girls, adolescent mothers, and for adolescents who are divorced or separated (Wodon, 2018). Boys are also subject to forced marriage – although in lower numbers – and their needs and interests should also be addressed in child protection interventions. Child protection supports children’s rights to information, expression and involvement in the decisions that affect them, so they can better protect themselves. Child protection is critical to realizing the wellbeing and rights of girls and boys. It is an essential operational and conceptual perspective that must be included in comprehensive approaches to prevent and respond to child marriage (UNICEF 2020)

According to UNICEF (2011) early marriage better known as child marriage is defined as marriage carried below the age 18 years before the girl is physically, physiologically and psychologically ready to shoulder the responsibilities of marriage and child bearing. Early marriage also means the individual becomes sexually active early, raising children while children themselves. The marriage of a young girl affects not only her life but the life of the children she will bear. According to AGHI (2003), both boys and girls are affected by child marriage but the issue impacts more negatively on girls in far larger number, with more intensity and is wide ranging. Child marriage is practiced with the belief that it reduces promiscuity among girls. This is purely because of the importance attached to virginity. Often time’s husbands want their wives to be virgins and for their parents, it is a great honour for their daughters to be found virgins by their husbands, and so girls are marriage off long before they attain maturity (Greene, 2015).

Where the system fails to work in the best interests of the child and is not gender-sensitive, it may cause further harm – in alternative dispute resolution systems where families negotiate to be compensated for their child having been raped, for example. In such contexts, the rights of girls and women are often overlooked in favour of male-dominated community-level conflict resolution. Like all adults working with children, child protection actors have an obligation to safeguard boys and girls in their care and to ensure that interventions and services do not harm them and are in their best interests. This requires mechanisms that protect children – in care homes, safe houses or shelters for girls at risk of child marriage – from further violence from the very people and institutions who should be keeping them safe (Gong, 2019).

Girls Not Brides (2020) has developed a ‘Theory of Change on Child Marriage’ to articulate what an effective response to child marriage entails. The Theory of Change outlines the range of approaches needed, demonstrates how they intersect and aims to provide a basis for identifying common indicators that could be used by diverse practitioners to monitor progress. The Theory of Change has been developed to facilitate greater partnership and collaboration among and across organizations, sectors and levels. It serves as a foundation to build consensus about actions needed to address child marriage and support married girls, in both the long and short-term. In addition, it provides a basis to understand where programming efforts are currently focused, in particular among Girls Not Brides members, and to highlight where further work is needed. In this sense, the Theory of Change offers both a mirror and a target (Girls Not Bride, 2016).

The majority of strategies to address child marriage fall within these categories: increasing school enrollment to offset the time spent participating in domestic labour, sustainable household economic support through cash/asset transfer; Civil Society Organizations’ empowering services. The three strategies are interlinked and mutually reinforcing; addressing child marriage will require a combination of actions related to all three. The specific combinations will be context-specific and depend on the drivers of child marriage in a given region. Activities are needed to empower girls and enable them to exercise their rights, for example through programmes which equip girls with training, skills, information, as well as the provision of safe spaces and support networks. Recognizing that girls are rarely the decision makers when it comes to child marriage, and that child marriage is often a deeply rooted practice in many communities, work is needed by CSOs with families and communities to create awareness of the harmful impact of child marriage, and of alternative roles for girls and women, so that families and communities prefer not to marry their daughters as children and so that they themselves engage in efforts to end the practice

Globally, the prevalence of child marriage is on a downward trajectory, falling from 51 percent in 1955 to 40 percent in 1990. However, the growth of the world’s adolescent population from 400 million in 1950 to 1.2 billion in 2010 means that the sheer number of married girls or girls at risk of being married at an early age is greater than at any point in history. More than one third of the world’s adolescent population resides in countries that are hot spots for child marriage, 338 million in South Asia and 94 million in West and Central Africa. While data on child marriage rates vary according to sources, most researchers agree that the problem is worse than it appears as the practice is generally underreported (UNFPA-UNICEF, 2020).

Once married, a girl’s world narrows dramatically. Child brides experience isolation from their family, friends and communities, as well as violence, abuse and exploitation. Girls who marry early often become pregnant while they are still children themselves, with great risks for their own well-being and that of their babies. There are clear links between child marriage and school drop-out with girls who are married before the age of 18 less likely to be in school than their peers, and girls who drop out of school more likely to be married. Child marriage – a marriage or union before the age 18 – has a disproportionate impact on girls. It curtails their education, compromises their health, exposes them to violence and traps them in poverty, undermining their prospects and potential (Wodon, 2017).

Child marriages in parts of Europe and Central Asia may reflect a hardening of gender attitudes that reinforce stereotypical roles for girls and limit their opportunities. Child marriage is often linked to patriarchal attitudes towards girls, including the need to safeguard family honour. Evidence suggests that child marriage increases during times of crisis with disproportionate negative impacts on girls. COVID-19, for instance, posed unique challenges. UNFPA estimates that an additional 13 million child marriages take place and society risks losing some of the substantial progress made against goals to reduce child marriage, particularly when we consider the likely impact of global school closures. Experience from other pandemics suggests that getting girls back into school is particularly challenging, with knock-on effects on child marriage (Stoner, 2019).

Recent World Bank analysis suggests that close to 7 million students from primary up to secondary education could drop out due to income shock related to COVID-19 alone. Whilst gender inequality is a root cause of child marriage, increased economic stresses, and family fears about the risks of violence against girls can also be drivers, particularly in times of crisis. Social protection can play a critical role in reducing income insecurity and enabling girls and boys to access education, two key pathways for delaying marriage. Yet few programmes deliberately and directly target child marriage in their objectives,

activities or monitoring and evaluation of results. The current evidence base on child marriage is mixed, leading social workers to voice concerns about social protection (Muchomba, 2021). This study explored: What is the current evidence base on the role of social protection in preventing child marriage, and where are the gaps in knowledge? How can social protection address child marriage, and what programme design characteristics might support better results in this area, particularly for adolescent girls? What can we learn from current child marriage programming and how can we make more effective links between child marriage, child protection, and social protection programming?

Objectives of the study

1. To determine the significant relationship between increasing school enrollment to offset time spent in participating in domestic labour and child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.
2. To investigate the relationship between sustainable household economic support through cash/asset transfer and early marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.
3. To examine the significant relationship existing between Civil Society Organization's child protection services and child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Research Questions

1. To what extent does increasing school enrollment to offset time spent participating in domestic labour significantly relate with early marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.?
2. How does sustainable household economic support through cash/asset transfer significantly relate with early marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.?
3. How do Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) child protection service significantly relate with early marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.?

Study hypotheses

1. Increasing school enrollment to offset time spent in participating in domestic labour has no significant relationship with child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.
2. Sustainable household income support through cash /asset transfer has no significant relationship with child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.
3. Civil Society Organization's child protection service has no significant with early marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Methodology

The descriptive survey design was used. This study was carried out in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State. The Local Government Area has a total of twelve (12) wards. Calabar South is in the southern part of Cross River State. Calabar South is located between longitude 8.341701 N and latitude 4.975716 E of the Greenwich Meridian. It has a landmark of 264km² and lies 4 meters above sea level. Calabar South has an estimated population of 291,700 from the 2022 population projection (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022).

Sample size/ sampling techniques

The sample for the study was made up of 400 respondents (registered mothers) selected from 12 wards of Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State. The sample comprised people living or staying in this local government area ranging from farmers, traders/business persons civil servants.

The researcher adopted the multi stage sampling technique in the study. The 12 wards constituted the 12 strata of the study. However, 1/8th of the strata was studied. This translated into 8 wards. These constituted the 8 clusters. To select the actual respondents, the systematic sampling technique was adopted. This involved enumerating all the houses in the clusters into even and odd numbers. The researcher studied even numbered houses. However, the researcher was particularly concerned with girls- mothers with or without children. Therefore, the purposive technique was adopted to study 50 respondents in each cluster. Through this method, a total of 50 respondents was selected per cluster. Therefore, the overall total number of respondents who participated in the study was 400. A 4 likert scale questionnaire that was put through validity and reliability test was used to elicit data from the respondents while chi square was used for the analysis.

Ethical consideration

A high level of ethical conduct was maintained throughout the research study. In particular was the fact that respondents were not compelled to take part in the research study

Presentation of Results

The analysis was based on 375 properly completed questionnaire. This represented 93.75 percent of total respondent.

Hypothesis 1: Increasing school enrollment to offset time spent in participating in domestic labour has no significant association with child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State. Chi-square (X^2) was employed to test data at 0.05 level of significant.

Table 1: Contingency table showing the association between increasing school enrollment and early child marriage.

Cell	O	E	O – E	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
1	205	190.67	14.33	205.3489	1.08
2	120	134.33	-14.33	205.3489	1.53
3	15	29.33	-14.33	205.3489	7.00
4	35	20.67	14.33	205.3489	9.93
Total	375				19.54

Field survey, 2024

Calculated (x^2) value	=	19.54
Critical (x^2) value	=	3.84
Level of significance	=	0.05
Degree of freedom	=	1

The result in Table 1 showed that the calculated (x^2) value of 19.54 is higher than critical (x^2) value of 3.84, 0.05 level of significance with 1degree of freedom. This result therefore implies that increasing school enrollment has a significant association with early child marriage.

Hypothesis 2: Sustainable household income support through cash /asset transfer has no significant association with early child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State. Chi-square (X^2) was employed to test data collected at 0.05 level of significant.

Table 2: Contingency table showing the association between sustainable household income support through cash/asset transfer and early child marriage

	O	E	O – E	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
1	190	165.09	24.91	620.5081	3.76
2	112	136.91	-24.91	620.5081	4.53
3	15	39.91	-24.91	620.5081	15.10
4	58	33.09	24.91	620.5081	18.75
Total	375				42.14

Field survey, 2024

Calculated (x^2) value	=	42.14
Critical (x^2) value	=	3.84
Level of significance	=	0.05
Degree of freedom	=	1

Results in table 3 show calculated (x^2) value of 42.14 is more than critical (x^2) of 3.84 at 0.05 significance level with 1 degree of freedom. The result therefore implies that sustainable household income support through cash/asset transfer has a significant association with early child marriage in the study area.

Hypothesis 3

Hypothesis three stated that Civil Society Organization’s child protection service has no significant association with early child marriage in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Table 3: Contingency table showing the association between Civil Society Organisation’s child protection service and early child marriage

Cell	O	E	O – E	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
1	130	106.6	23.4	547.56	5.14
2	75	98.4	-23.4	547.56	5.56
3	65	88.4	-23.4	547.56	6.19
4	105	81.6	23.4	547.57	6.71
Total	375				23.60

Field survey, 2024

Calculated (x ²) value	=	23.60
Critical (x ²) value	=	3.84
Level of significance	=	0.05
Degree of freedom	=	1

The result shows calculated (x²) value of 23.60 is more than critical (x²) value of 3.84 needed at 0.05 level of significance with 1 degree of freedom. The result therefore implies that Civil Society Organization’s child protection service has significant association with early child marriage in the study area.

Discussion of Findings

Increasing girls’ school enrollment to offset time spent in participating in domestic labour and early child marriage

The analysis implies the existence of a significant association between increasing school enrollment to offset time spent participating in domestic labour impacts on child marriage. According to Misunes, Gaston and Cappa (2015) education for girls is one of the best strategies for protecting girls against child marriage. When they are able to stay in school and avoid being married early, girls can build a foundation for a better life for themselves and their families. And if they have already been married young, access to education, economic opportunities and health services—including HIV prevention and sexual and reproductive health— help enrich their lives and enhance their future (Greene 2015). Despite security challenges, the education sector plans in six north-west Nigerian states led to a significant increase in girls’ enrollment in secondary schools and a reduction in the percentage of girls married before the age of 18, a new report has shown. It further pointed to an inter-sectionality between the two outcome indicators – enrollment and early marriage. Jigawa State, with the highest increase in enrollment for girls at the basic education level, was also the state with the second most significant reduction in the age of marriage. Conversely, Kaduna State, which experienced the lowest change in enrollment rates for girls within the same period, also experienced the least change in the age of marriage for girls among the six states

The findings support Okeke (2004) that in traditional African society, the role of the female was pegged and circumscribed. It was considered a taboo sending a female to school. This is because of the attitude towards education for women. It was considered a waste of money, time and effort considering that most women in no time get married into another family, to raise the children that serve as farm hands for their father. In addition to raising the children for the man, the women still helped to keep the house and provide meal for all. Hence the saying some years back that women’s education ends in the kitchen. This primitive attitude exposes women to early marriage (Okeke, 2004; Ocho, 1988).

As observed by Gong (2019), progress has been limited, particularly in West Africa, one of the world’s child marriage hot spots. Five of the 10 countries with the highest rates of child marriage worldwide are in West Africa. In 2011, of 14.9 million females in West Africa between the ages of 20 and 24 years, 6.2 million, or 42 percent, were married before the age of 18.3 With 167 million people, Nigeria has the largest population of married girls in Africa: 39.4 percent of all females in Nigeria between the ages of 20 to 24 were married before the age of 18 by 2011. Education for girls is one of the best strategies for protecting girls against child marriage. When they are able to stay in school and avoid being married early, girls can build a foundation for a better life for themselves and their families. And if they have already been married young, access to education, economic opportunities and health services—including HIV prevention and sexual and reproductive health— help enrich their lives and enhance their future.

Sustainable household income support through cash /asset transfer and early child marriage

The analysis shows a significant association between sustainable household income support through cash transfer and child marriage. Social protection especially cash transfer programmes – can play a role in mitigating some of the economic and social drivers of child marriage in both development and humanitarian contexts. Poverty and economic insecurity are closely linked with child marriage, but create different incentives for marriage depending on local marriage practices and norms. These

practices and norms affect how a cash transfer may impact on the timing of marriage. Improved household economic security is possible with cash transfer (Gong 2019). By increasing a household's ability to meet their basic needs, cash transfers can reduce pressure on families to shift economic responsibility for a girl to her husband's household, especially when a bride price is expected. They can also reduce girls' own motivation to seek economic security through marriage or high-risk sexual relationships. Cash transfers can reduce the risk of child marriage and early sexual debut by keeping girls in school for longer, especially where married girls are excluded from school. In addition, girls who spend longer in school can gain more knowledge and skills, and raise aspirations, empowering them to make (or to influence) decisions to marry later and support later marriage for their own children (Handa, 2014)

Findings support Muchomba (2021) that cash transfers can mitigate several of the economic and social drivers of child marriage through different pathways. Conditional cash transfers (CCT) play an important role in keeping girls in school and are most consistent at reducing the risk of child marriage across marriage contexts. They counteract family and social pressures to marry, and reduce the risk of self-initiated unions and pre-marital sexual relationships that may lead to pregnancy and marriage. Unconditional cash transfers (UCT) are often effective at increasing access to school and in protecting against early and high-risk sex, but this does not generally reduce child marriage. This is partly because the girls whose families choose to use UCTs to help them stay in school are already at lower risk of child marriage. However, cash transfers can alleviate the economic pressures to marry or form a union in some circumstances (Muchomba, 2021).

Malhotra and Elnakib (2021) documented that programmes in Malawi and the Philippines show that the impact of both UCTs and CCTs on household economic security can reduce the risk of child marriage, especially where social norms for child marriage are weaker, poverty is a main driver, and transfers are regular and predictable. This is likely because CCTs incentivise school attendance among girls who are at risk of child marriage, while UCTs may only support attendance among girls who are already at lower risk of marriage. There is also evidence – from Bangladesh and Malawi – that by supporting girls to gain knowledge and raise their aspirations, cash transfers that increase educational attainment can empower them to make (or to influence) decisions to delay marriage. The Bangladesh Development Society and Save the Children implemented Kishoree Kontha – “Adolescent Girl's Voice” – is one of the largest adolescent empowerment programmes ever implemented in low-income countries. Activities: Communities identified safe spaces where girls could meet five to six days a week to socialize and access educational support and social competency training. In half of the empowerment communities, the programme also included financial literacy training. The conditional incentive programme delivered cooking oil to families with unmarried girls aged 15 to 17. Community volunteers distributed ration cards to these girls at the start of the programme. Every four months between April 2008 and August 2010, girls who remained unmarried could collect cooking oil by presenting their ration card to community volunteers at a distribution point in the community, who would then confirm the girls' marital status with other community members. The value of the oil was approximately US\$16 per year, an amount chosen to offset the estimated increase in dowry for every additional year a girl remains unmarried (Malhotra & Elnakib, 2021).

Four years after the programme ended, a study was conducted of all girls who were unmarried and aged 15 to 17 at the beginning of the programme. Parents were asked about daughters' current marital status, childbearing history and school enrolment. Researchers found that: The conditional incentives led to a significant reduction in child marriage and adolescent childbearing, and increased educational attainment. The empowerment programme increased educational attainment but did not affect child marriage or adolescent childbearing. Taken together, these results suggest that a conditional incentive for families of adolescent girls can lead to substantial reductions in child marriage and adolescent childbearing in a setting with high rates of child marriage. Unlike incentives conditional on schooling which only focus on girls in schools, this incentive programme – in which marriage was the conditionality – also had positive effects for out-of-school girls (Handa, 2014).

Civil Society Organization's child protection services and early child marriage

Analysis revealed that civil society organization's services are significantly associated with child marriage. As admitted by Misunas, Gaston and Cappa (2019) scaling up child protection systems that prevent and respond to child marriage requires much larger allocations of public resources. CSOs can play an important role in tracking spending and advocating to governments to allocate larger budgets to finance child protection systems, including for an expanded and better-trained social service workforce. The Global Programme to End Child Marriage ('the Global Programme') aims to have a catalytic effect and works with many partners to advocate for and support practical actions to end child marriage, and promote gender equality and the rights of adolescent girls (Misunas, Gaston & Cappa, 2019). CSOs carry out advocacy and capacity building for local communal authorities to integrate child protection budget lines into communal budgets. Promoting the agency of young people and civil society in those communities to gain knowledge of child rights-sensitive budgeting and to hold local authorities accountable with regards to child protection-related budget lines, including on child marriage (Misuna et al, 2019).

CSOs continually and consciously educate, sensitize and create public awareness on the effects and risk relating to child marriage. They raise public awareness and campaigns to end child marriage using the media/ social media, outreaches at mosques, churches and communities. Public sensitization takes place in both the urban and rural areas. Furthermore, CSOs educate citizens on the health effects of early and forced marriage. Young girls who have been victims are able to share their experiences with other young girls, families and people in the communities. Public awareness creation, campaigns, education and sensitization focus on educating the citizens to change their perceptions, behaviours and attitudes towards girls and women in the society. Moreover, during these sensitization activities, laws regarding child rights issues and their sexuality are articulated (The Alliance for Child Protection in Humanitarian Action 2020). CSOs take interest in schooling on the legal age of marriage and the fact that marrying young girls before the legal age is a criminal offence punishable by law. CSOs intensify advocacy for policy reforms and comprehensive legislation that promote child rights and protection. Activists also advocate for the clarification of ambiguous legislations between religious, customary and civil marriages. They sometimes demand the official registration of all marriages and advocate for law enforcement in communities. In addition, CSOs campaign for the same minimum legal age of marriage for both female and male. At both national and local levels, CSOs organize fora with all stakeholders supportive of ending child marriage and raise awareness among them on the state of early and forced marriage in the country and the need to address it by embarking on policy reforms that seek to empower girls (CEDAW & UNCRC, 2014). Findings support UNICEF (2017) that CSOs provide service support interventions for adolescent girls, survivors, child wives and the family. Poverty is one underlying cause of child marriage globally. CSOs' supportive interventions seek to empower girls so they become economically equipped to be independent. Basic and secondary education should be accessible to young girls while child marriage victims/ survivors should be reintegrated into the educational system or in vocational training institutes. The creation of adolescent-friendly health services and youth counselling centres in local communities where the youth can get information about their reproductive health issues and support will be invaluable in bridging the information gap.

Conclusion

Child marriage happens in all parts of the world and is not associated with any particular culture or religion. A greater percentage of women in developing countries married before their 18th birthday. Early marriage serves as a threat to a child's future development. This is because it is difficult to have access to quality education and higher education and it limits the ability to secure a good job. Also, girls involved in early marriage face poverty conditions. Therefore, social protection can play a critical role in reducing income insecurity and enabling girls to access education; two key pathways for delaying child marriage. There is a broader evidence that social protection such as increasing girls' school enrollment to offset time spent in participating in domestic labour, sustainable household income support through cash /asset transfer and Civil Society Organization's child protection services can often have protective impacts.

Recommendations

Based on this empirical evidence:

1. It is critical that girls should have options aside from marriage and motherhood
2. Social protection should be viewed as necessary conditions for addressing some (but not all) of the drivers of child marriage
3. The policy makers should be encouraged to improve social welfare for girls especially promoting school enrollment for them to pursue education, cash and stipends can help them in school too.
4. The Federal Ministry of Women Affairs and Civil Society Organizations (government and Non-government sectors) should evolve strategies to facilitate sustainable response to end child marriage and all the associated ills.

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